

D8.12

Final conference / Final Impact Report

BBTWINS

Agri-Food Value Chain
Digitalisation for
Resource Efficiency

**Circular
Bio-based
Europe**
Joint Undertaking

**Bio-based Industries
Consortium**

Horizon 2020
European Union Funding
for Research & Innovation

PROJECT	BBTWINS
PROJECT NUMBER	101023334
PROJECT TITLE	Digital twins for the optimisation of agrifood value chain processes and the supply of quality biomass for bio-processing
PROGRAM	H2020-BBI-JTI-2020
START DATE	1 JUN 2021
DURATION	48 months
DELIVERABLE NUMBER	D8.12
DELIVERABLE TITLE	Final conference / Final Impact Report
SCHEDULE DATE & MONTH	30 04 2025
ACTUAL SUB. DATE & MONTH	28 04 2025
LEAD BENEFICIARY NAME	REVOLVE
TYPE OF DELIVERABLE	Report
DISSEMINATION LEVEL	PUBLIC

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This project has received funding from the Bio-based Industries Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 101023334.

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Glossary, abbreviations and acronyms

AI	Artificial intelligence
EU	European Union
R&D	Research and development
R&D&I	Research, development and innovation
IoT	Internet of Things

1. Introduction

Bio-Based Digital Twins (BBTWINS) aims to overcome the challenges faced by the EU agri-food sector's transition to become more sustainable by developing a digital platform for the optimisation of agri-food value chain processes and the supply of quality biomass for processing. BBTWINS combines blockchain, artificial intelligence (machine learning and deep learning), big data, software analytics, computer simulation of agri-food processes, and the Internet of Things (IoT), in this single platform.

With 13 partners in 7 countries, the BBTWINS consortium have been focusing on meat and fruit production, integrating the value chain (from crop to final product) and will define the optimal pathway for each feedstock to maximise efficiency and minimise losses – without impacting quality.

The final conference was an event titled “BioByte: Digital Technologies for a Resilient Agri-food sector” held in Brussels, Belgium, on 1 April 2025. The forum was hosted by the BBTWINS Project, and participants were able to hear from experts, explore real-world replication cases, and join interactive panels to discover how innovative digital tools can enhance sustainability, reduce waste, and create new revenue streams. Stakeholders from the industry, policymakers, academics, and others came together to discuss potential solutions for more sustainable value chain optimisation with the help of digital and circular technologies. The event was also livestreamed as a digital summit for viewers around the world.

2. Agenda

2.1. Welcome and keynote

The final BBTWINS event opened with a welcome from Perna Humpal (REVOLVE), who highlighted the project's contributions to bridging the gap between innovation and implementation in the agri-food sector. She acknowledged the growing adoption of digital tools like AI and digital twins of the food industry, while also pointing out the challenges of ensuring accessibility and balancing innovation with tradition.

Joining online, Ana Ruiz Sierra, Programme Officer at the Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking (CBE JU), congratulated the consortium for their achievements and encouraged further steps towards commercialisation to strengthen the European bioeconomy.

Daniel de la Puente, BBTWINS Project Coordinator and Head of EU Projects at CNTA, reflected on the project's evolution and the power of teamwork. He underlined how BBTWINS demonstrated practical applications of AI — from estimating pig weight without scales to improving traceability and valorising fruit waste. While some tech trends come and go, he noted, digital twins have proven their long-term value for real-world agri-food challenges.

Figure 1 Daniel de la Puente, BBTWINS Coordinator, presenting his opening keynote

2.2. Partner pitches

The first session of the event showcased real-world applications of AI, blockchain, process simulation, logistics optimisation, and digital twins. In a dynamic series of partner pitches, experts from the consortium presented key innovations developed throughout the project, offering insight into the practical applications of these digital tools across the meat and fruit value chains. From AI-driven image recognition to advanced process modelling, the session highlighted best practices and lessons learned. The session concluded with a Q&A moderated by Prerna Humpal, sparking engaging discussion with both in-person and online participants.

The pitches from session 1 were provided by:

- *Rebeca Martínez de Laguna, R&D Engineer at PANOImagen*
- *Israel Serrano, Founder of StelvioTech*
- *Mónica Mendiola Lanao, Researcher R&D&I in Food Processes at CNTA*
- *Ruben Guisson, MooV Manager at VITO*
- *Toni Lastusilta, Senior Scientist at VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd*
- *José M^a Alonso Rodríguez (Cacho), Innovation Coordinator, SOLTEC Ingenieros SL*

The second session focused on how BBTWINS technologies can be applied beyond the project, with a particular emphasis on industry use cases, sustainability assessment, and replication potential. Speakers addressed key topics such as reducing paperwork for farmers through data interoperability, unlocking the value of data spaces in the agri-food sector, and tools to scale digital twin technologies more efficiently. The session concluded with a Q&A moderated by Sudhanshu Verma, offering the audience a chance to engage with the presenters on practical pathways forward.

The pitches from session 2 were provided by:

- *André Ribeiro, RTD Researcher at Center for Waste Valorization (CVR)*
- *Sergio José Ramos, R&D&I Director of Naturuel S.L.*
- *Magdalena Jaskiewicz, Researcher at ANGAZ Tech*
- *Athanasios Lampropoulos, EU R&D Project Manager at CluBE-Cluster of Bioeconomy and Environment of Western Macedonia*

2.3. Expert talks

Two invited experts offered external perspectives on the digital transition in agri-food.

Kieran Sullivan from the Walton Institute at South East Technological University in Ireland highlighted the foundational role of data in enabling digital twins, while cautioning that collecting, structuring, and formatting data is far from straightforward. He stressed the importance of interoperability—not just at the technical level, but also between people and organisations across the supply chain. In such a diverse sector, both in terms of geography and production systems, interoperability and trust are essential.

Jürgen Vangeyte from ILVO echoed the centrality of data, emphasising that meaningful progress in AI and digital technologies is only possible when high-quality data is available. He illustrated the current challenge of "data spaghetti" and the need to shift towards a more circular, integrated data ecosystem that can fully support the potential of digital tools in agriculture.

2.4. Roundtable discussion

The final part of the day brought together expert panellists to reflect on the key barriers to scaling digital tools in agriculture. A major focus was the challenge of managing and sharing high-quality data across stakeholders. Speakers agreed that a more professionalised approach—such as hiring dedicated data officers—could help bridge the gap between data producers and users. Interoperability, transparency, and a deeper understanding of consumer needs emerged as recurring themes. Increasing trust and encouraging producers to share data confidently and securely was seen as a critical next step in advancing the sector's digital transition.

The four panellists were:

- *Jürgen Vangeyte, Scientific Director of Agricultural Engineering at ILVO*
- *Malamati Louta, member of BBTWINS External Advisory Board and Professor & Director at the Telecommunication Networks and Advanced Services Laboratory of University of Western Macedonia*
- *Hermann Bohrer, member of BBTWINS External Advisory Board and retired executive from BMW Group*
- *Athanasios Lampropoulos, EU R&D Project Manager at CluBE-Cluster of Bioeconomy and Environment of Western Macedonia*

The discussion was moderated by Sudhanshu Verma, Head of Growth at REVOLVE.

Figure 2 Four panelists at the roundtable discussion moderated by Sudhanshu Verma

3. Impact

3.1. Attendance¹

With 102 registrants total registered via HubSpot, the online public livestream reached 174 unique viewers, 45 on the day of the event, with a peak of 26 concurrent viewers. The recording of the livestream reached 77 (session 1) and 60 (session 2) at the time of the submission of the report. 44 people clicked on the event's LinkedIn page, amplifying the reach within these respondents' network. Regarding professional background of total registrants, 43% came from research or academia, followed by 8% from the private sector/industry, 4% policymakers, 16% industry, and 9% media.

Figure 3 Attendees getting to know each other

¹ Sources of exact numbers are HubSpot (used for registration and mailing campaign), Zoom Analytics (streaming platform used) and YouTube Analytics (platform storing recordings of the sessions).

3.2. Dissemination strategy

To maximize reach and engagement for BioByte: Digital Technologies for a Resilient Agri-food Sector, a multi-pronged dissemination strategy was implemented. This approach combined targeted digital outreach, stakeholder engagement, and personalized marketing to ensure high visibility and effective registration conversion across key demographics within the agri-food innovation ecosystem.

3.2.1. DIRECT MARKETING

Direct marketing efforts centered on a comprehensive email campaign targeting stakeholders, industry professionals, and academic institutions with vested interests in digital transformation within the agri-food sector. A total of **34 academic institutions** across Europe—such as **ETH Zürich, University of Bologna, KU Leuven, University of Padua, and Université Libre de Bruxelles**—were contacted, focusing on departments and programs with a strong emphasis on agri-tech and digitalization.

In parallel, **11 EU/national-funded projects**, representing **40 individual contacts**, were engaged. These included flagship initiatives like **Trans-e-Bio, SmartAgriHubs, ModernAkis, and EUFarmBook**, ensuring outreach to professionals already active in digital transformation of the agri-food sector.

To enhance credibility and network effect, **14 clustering platforms and innovation initiatives**—such as **Bio-based Industries Consortium, Foodvalley, and Bio Base Europe Pilot Plant**—were mobilized to share event information within their respective communities. Additionally, **6 policymakers** were personally invited to foster public-private dialogue.

3.2.2. SOCIAL MEDIA

LinkedIn was the core social media channel, employed through both **organic** and **paid** strategies. Organic efforts included **three posts per week**, featuring speaker spotlights, informational carousels, and engagement-driven content aligned with themes such as **AI, blockchain, and digital twins** in agriculture.

A **EUR 1,000 paid LinkedIn campaign** was executed to drive registrations from both in-person attendees in Belgium and online participants across Europe. The boosted campaign ran over 12 days with a total budget of €1,000 (approx. €85/day), optimized for event registrations.

Rather than broad job functions, the campaign focused on specific job titles to ensure precise audience alignment. For in-person attendance, targeting covered Brussels, Ghent, Leuven, and Antwerp, focusing on industries such as **agri-tech, biotechnology, and F&B manufacturing**. Job titles included **PhD candidates, postdoctoral researchers, R&D managers, AgTech consultants, and Innovation leads**. Interest filters included followers of **EIT Food, CBE JU, and FOOD 4 FUTURE**, as well as skills in **digital agriculture, AI, and blockchain**.

For online participation, the campaign extended to Belgium, the Netherlands, Germany, France, Spain, Greece, and the UK. Target job titles included **CTOs**, **Digital Transformation Managers**, and **Smart Farming Specialists**, within industries such as **AI**, **smart farming**, and **food manufacturing**.

The [event's LinkedIn page](#) featured a clear call to action—"Register Now"—paired with a banner highlighting AI, blockchain, and agri-tech themes. Messaging emphasized the event's relevance to sustainable food systems.

The campaign was amplified through partner and speaker networks. Promotional toolkits (see registration invite in Annex A) were distributed to all consortium partners, encouraging them to share posts within their professional networks. This tactic significantly extended the campaign's organic reach and added peer-to-peer credibility. Combining paid promotion with organic amplification ensured strong engagement and contributed significantly to event registrations.

4. Conclusions

The final BBTWINS conference highlighted how digital innovations are transforming the agri-food sector by making value chains more efficient, sustainable, and circular. From AI and blockchain to interoperability and smart logistics, the event showcased practical applications of these technologies and their role in optimising processes across the entire value chain. Central to the discussions was the importance of involving producers early on, ensuring that digital solutions are both usable and impactful in real-world settings.

Key takeaways included the potential of waste valorisation, the benefits of real-time data for smarter decision-making, and the critical need for interoperability and trust to drive adoption at scale. A big thank you to all who contributed to this successful gathering in Brussels and online.

The full event recordings and presentation slides are available [online](#) for anyone who would like to revisit the insights shared.

Figure 4 Group photo of the BBTWINS consortium present at the final event in Brussels.

Annex

Annex A- Registration invite (screenshot)

The BIO BYTE

BBTWINS
Agri-Food Value Chain
Digitalisation for
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REGISTRATIONS NOW OPEN!

1 APRIL 2025 | 09:30 - 14:30 CET

BioByte: Digital Technologies for a Resilient Agri-food sector

Brussels & Online

BBi JJ BBTWINS

The [BBTWINS](#) project coordinators and partners would like to warmly invite you to **BioByte: Digital Technologies for a Resilient Agri-food sector**, a hybrid event taking place on Tuesday, 1st April from 9:30-14:30 (GMT+2) in Brussels and online.

How can digital technologies boost resilient, resource-efficient value chains? Hear from experts, explore real-world replication cases, and join interactive panels to discover how innovative digital tools can enhance sustainability, reduce waste, and create new revenue streams.

The event will dive into the practical use of technologies like artificial vision, sensors, blockchain-based traceability and digital twins tackling challenges from crop production to biomass valorisation.

Register now!

In-person attendance is limited, and spots will be allocated on a confirmed basis. Please finalize any travel arrangements only after receiving confirmation of your in-person participation.

Registration is required for both in-person and online attendance [via this link](#). Livestream access details will be provided closer to the event date.

Confirm your attendance on LinkedIn and stay connected with industry experts! [Join here](#).

For the preliminary agenda and further information, follow the link below. Should you have any questions, contact dorottya@revolve.media.

We look forward to welcoming you!

Event details